

IMPROVEMENT OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES THROUGH ECOLOGICAL EDUCATION OF PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT: This article provides information on the improvement of modern pedagogical technologies through environmental education of preschool children

KEY WORDS: preschool education, ecology, preparatory group, pedagogue, educator, child's outlook.

Ecological knowledge is the structure, development, change of living nature, the condition of living creatures on the earth, their relationships with each other and the environment, the quantity and quality, size, types of natural resources, and the way to save and use them economically. consists of mastering them.

Giving children ecological education and training, starting from the first time they step into nature, throughout their whole life, to use nature consciously and rationally, to educate the traditions of our people that treat nature with respect and attention, to increase natural resources and to be full of them. It is to teach children to use tools, to organize gardens and flower beds, to take care of trees, plants and animals, not to harm them, to instill good qualities in the hearts of children towards nature and its preservation.

The main goal of ecological education is to form knowledge, skills and abilities in preschool children to have a conscious attitude to the environment and its problems and to find optimal solutions for them.

To achieve this goal, it is necessary to solve a number of tasks.

1. To teach our children of preschool age to conserve and consciously protect their habitat (nature) and resources in environmental education.

2. Formation of ecological culture. First of all, it should start from the family. There are the following ways to introduce preschool children to nature:

- Conducting trainings;
- Excursion;
- Labor;
- Games;
- Activities of daily living.

Excursions are one of the main methods of education in preschool educational organizations in introducing children to nature. During the excursion, children will get a clear idea of nature by seeing, feeling, and hearing. In the course of the excursion, preschoolers develop realistic ideas about the laws of nature.

Experiments conducted at the experimental testing ground at the Science and Nature Center arouse interest in children and encourage them to make new inventions. This center is also the center of the greatest opportunity for children to learn about nature and its phenomena. If the activity of the center is properly organized, children will learn 90% of the

knowledge about nature. The center arouses interest not only in children, but also in pedagogues. The information about where the things used in our life come from, what is obtained from them, the children sprinkled the seeds in pots with their own hands, put water in them and the seeds germinated.

The didactic game is considered the main form of education, and it becomes a form of learning that is easy, fast and the acquisition of knowledge that is not intended by children in advance. For example, "Is the name of this animal included in the Red Book?" "Find this animal" game. The teacher makes the children stand in a circle, calls out the name "hai von" and throws the ball to a child. The child picks up the ball and says whether it is included in the "Red Book" or not. When developing the content of the game about nature protection, the relationship between people, their humaneness and care for the natural environment should be in the central place. Therefore, when using such games, it is necessary to take into account the age of children and develop games according to their age.

As in any process, educators try to use all the teaching methods and techniques available to them. There are several forms of environmental education in preschool educational organizations. These are: Visual, practical, verbal

Visual method - it is better to show once than to tell a hundred times, especially about children and their relationship with nature. Visual methods in environmental education: observations, viewing pictures, showing models, slide show. Visual methods are fully compatible with the abilities of children's cognitive activity, allowing them to form vivid, clear ideas about nature.

Practical method - games, experiments, modeling. The use of these methods allows the teacher to clarify and deepen thoughts and introduce the knowledge he has acquired into the system by establishing connections and relationships between individual objects and natural phenomena. Practical methods are very important for the full integration of children into ecological culture.

1. Modeling. The modeling method is very suitable for primary and secondary children. This is the replacement of real things (events) with the help of schemes, symbols, figures or images. Simulation helps to give children a general understanding of the object being studied.

2. Experiments and experiments. Experience in environmental education is the observation of the studied object in specially created conditions. The experiment must have a purpose and a purpose. It is necessary to think about the process of experimentation, as well as technologies and tools. The experience itself is logically completed orally or in writing.

3. Environmental games. Didactic, mobile, desktop or oral - the game is to know, know and reinforce the material. The game is widely used by kindergarten teachers as a method of environmental education, because the game is a leading activity of preschool age. Therefore, through the development of environmental education in preschool children, a foundation is created for the formation of their love for nature and mastery of natural sciences in the future. Environmental education for children and the use of modern methods have good results. In addition, I would suggest the use of modern technologies in teaching the children of the preparatory group. This technology is gradually developing in our country. Through this, it is possible to further improve children's mastery and organize an interesting, new educational process.

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